

OPTIMIZING THE DEPLOYMENT OF NEW TECHNOLOGIES IN URBAN SEARCH AND RESCUE OPERATIONS – SYNERGISE*

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ABSTRACT

Modern Search and Rescue (SAR) operations depend on reliable and efficient new technologies, capable of supporting the First Responder (FR) teams in the field and at the same time addressing real-world gaps and requirements. The SYNERGISE project designs, develops, integrates, deploys, tests, validates and demonstrates a Novel Integrated Toolkit for Collaborative Response and Enhanced Situational Awareness (NIT-CRES) toolkit, at the service of response agencies, which ensures an upgrade to managing of complex incidents. The NIT-CRES armors the FRs at all fronts by delivering novel, affordable, accepted, and customized response tools and services as part of their operational assets. Notably, the toolkit abides to privacy, ethical, security and legal constraints by design, considers an increased degree of inclusiveness for its operators and its set-up facilitates collaborative response addressing standard operating procedures.

Keywords: Search & Rescue, First Responders, crisis management, emergency response, flood, wildfire.

1. INTRODUCTION

In Search and Rescue (SAR) operations, the First Responders (FR) are called upon to act in a very wide range of environments, conditions and limitations, associated to both external and internal factors. Weather, location, access, local infrastructure, travel time, are only some of these external factors, while team's readiness level, organization, skill level and experience, toolkits available, are a few of the most important internal factors.

For Urban Search and Rescue (USAR) the most critical factor, besides FR safety, is speed. Every USAR mission is an effort against time, beginning as a speed race during the first few hours after the disaster event and gradually becoming a marathon run as the hotzone gets cleared in a more focused way. The FR teams must be capable both physically and mentally in adapting to this shifting working environment and every new challenge that emerges, keeping track of risks and possible hazards, while at the same time exploiting the probabilities of survival for the victims still trapped or undiscovered inside the disaster zone.

Similarly, in floods or fires there are capability gaps and technological needs for such SAR missions, some of which are commonly shared while others are specific to the type of SAR mission. For example, in fire the situation is highly dynamic and, thus, both supporting infrastructure and victim handling need to be highly mobile and adaptive. In floods, the escalation is usually observable (unless it is a catastrophic

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structure collapse) and mostly predictable, yet large populations may be exposed to immediate danger during the event, as well as due to isolation for several days after the main event.

Based on these observations, it is important to point out factors for properly planning, designing and developing SAR-related technologies for actual field deployment in real-world environments. In practice, the questions that need to be answered by any such new technology are:

- What does it bring to the FR team in the field as added value in operational level?
- What are its benefits and constraints in the tactical / technical level?
- How does it relate to existing practices and similar assets already in use?
- What is the integration and training plan in order to be fully operational?

The following sections describe the methodological approach and the evaluation process implemented by the SYNERGISE project, incorporating the domain expertise of both technical and FR partners.

2. METHODOLOGY – DESCRIPTION OF WORK

Beginning from the kick-off of the project on September 2023, the project explored and analyzed the technological aspects of FR field operations in various types of SAR missions, focused specifically on how to improve the safety and the effectiveness of these FR teams.

This comprises of multitude of tools and services required for boosting situational awareness and sense-making by offering the means to autonomously and synergistically perform indoor and outdoor exploration of incident sites. The purpose is towards victim identification whilst receiving at all times information about responders' position and vitals, as well as analyses of passive and active threats and hazards at the area of operations. In addition, it should upgrade collaborative response to an incident, as well as resources management by continuously sharing and updating the Common Operational Picture (COP) across deployed FR teams, among the chain of command and between participating agencies.

Given the experiences, observations and limitations, various gaps and areas of need for technological improvement emerge in relation to how SAR operations may be supported:

- FR safety at the personal level (gear, wearables, localization, physiological parameters).
- Team safety via hazard mapping, coordination, monitoring.
- Area assessment, marking, dynamic mapping, movement coverage (especially indoors).
- Fast automated visual screening of images, videos, maps (for victims and hazards).
- Remote sensing via multiple modalities (visual, chemical, sound, seismic, etc).
- Remotely operated or fully autonomous robots, putting distance between FRs and the scene.
- Automated access routing and navigation for the FR team.
- Mini-robotics & soft-robotics, used for specific tasks (e.g. search shafts).
- Victim detection, localization, access discovery, medical assessment.
- Indoor positioning & tactical communications (intra-team and team-C3).
- Augmented situational awareness for the FR team via VR/AR tools.

It should also be mentioned that the assets and tools used by the FRs may be used or reconfigured in a way not initially intended by the developer, if it makes sense operationally for addressing a specific problem at hand. For example, it is not uncommon for FR teams to use simple devices like a typical smartwatch with a cardiac pulse sensor (HR indicator) on a victim as an additional tool during secondary

assessment / monitoring or a similar GPS-enabled gadget as geolocation “tagging” for a victim that may move, e.g. sink deeper inside debris or drift away during a flood. This means that adaptability, modularity and interoperability of any such new SAR-related technology are as important as the core functionality intended by design.

The SYNERGISE project is different compared to other R&D project for SAR-related technologies: Instead of focusing exclusively on the requirements on specific types of SAR missions or of individual FR organizations in their consortiums, it draws seeds and aggregated conclusions from the FR background, previous R&D works, as well as recent progress in SAR technologies that is either already in use or identified by several actors as important to have. This material is summarized by the International Forum to Advance First Responder Innovation (IFAFRI) as a guideline of ten common global capability gaps, technically described by FR organizations around the world [2].

These technological gaps are addressed by developing an integrated toolkit for improved management of natural and man-made disasters, which includes:

- UxVs swarm consisting of aerial, legged and snake-like robots for autonomous area assessment and victims detection.
- Wearables for real-time monitoring of FR physiological parameters, gas/environmental sensing for potential toxics and explosives detection.
- Advanced localization systems for indoor and outdoor operations.
- Augmented reality (AR) for remote control and rich map visualization for FRs.
- AI-enabled information fusion for improved decision-making.
- Rapidly deployable tactical communications for robust data exchange.
- An interoperable Incident Management System (IMS) for C3 operations.

These innovative solutions and new tools will equip FR teams with capabilities and assets that will: (a) improve situational awareness both indoors and outdoors, personally and also collaboratively as a team, (b) reliable localization, tracking and physiological parameters monitoring of FRs, (c) boost the Common Operational Picture (COP) capabilities via rich sensing and AI-enabled data fusion, (d) provide interoperable and compatible tools for FRs according to their real-world operational needs.

3. PILOTING EVENTS – FIELD TRIALS

The NIT-CRES developed by the SYNERGISE project will be provided at the service of the SAR personnel, fire brigades, emergency medical, police and civil protection agencies for extensive testing, training and validation, at component and Toolkit levels.

More specifically, several levels and scales of laboratory and field testing activities are included in the core Description of Work, in the context of real-world SAR operations [3,4]. These are focused on evaluating the framework of rich Integration, Testing and Validation Activities Programme – of Round Tables (RTs), Collaborative Lab Tests (CLTs), Technical Integration Workshop (TIWS), Component Field Tests (CFTs) and System Field Tests (SFTs) – towards empowering collaborative response and handling of complex incidents to its fullest.

The four major field testing events at the component level are the CFTs, described in Table 1. There are three CFTs already conducted successfully, with iterations and improvements of each component based on extensive FT feedback. The fourth CFT is planned for October 2025.

Table 1. Plan and description of Component Field Tests (CFT) in the SYNERGISE project.

CFT1	Localization services (indoor/outdoor), Field and HQ Communications, Vitals and Gas Wearables	M15	Greece	HRTA (L), SYSNAV, ETRI, ASTRIAL, WEARIN, All users, TNO, PLUSETHICS 2 nd Component Field test in which technologies are tested in a realistic environment. Scenario: Urban Search and Rescue [Duration: 2-4 days]
CFT2	C3I/IMS, Augmented Reality Services, OWL	M19	Poland	CNBOP (L), ASTRIAL, CERTH, VIRNECT, NTNU, All users, TNO, PLUSETHICS 1 st Component Field test in which technologies are tested in a realistic environment. Scenario: Train Accident involving explosion and fire [Duration: 2-4 days]
CFT3	C3I/IMS, Augmented Reality Services, OWL, Localization services (indoor/outdoor), Field and HQ Communications, Vitals and Gas Wearables	M22	Sweden	SBFF (L), ASTRIAL, CERTH, VIRNECT, NTNU, SYSNAV, ETRI, WEARIN, All users, TNO, PLUSETHICS 3 rd Component Field test in which technologies are tested in a realistic environment. Scenario: Surface and Underground search and rescue involving explosion and fire [Duration: 3-5 days]
CFT4	All SYNERGISE Tools	M26	Switzerland	ETH (L), All consortium 4 th Component Field test in which technologies are tested in a realistic environment. Scenario: Surface and Underground search and rescue involving explosion and fire [Duration: 3-5 days]

Figure 1. The SYNERGISE team at Botkyrka, Sweden, during the 3rd Component Field Test (CFT3), June 2025.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The SYNERGISE project extends previous experience and integrates the practices of involving end-user organizations very early on in the development process, in order to have continuous evaluation and feedback. Furthermore, it implements a plan of extensive field trials throughout its timeline, not only in the full pilots but also in multiple small-scale events, where the technologies and prototypes under development will be tested, evaluated and validated. The project started officially on September 2023 and it will evolve in a period of 42 months.

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